

Strategy Implementation: Workforce Utilization and employment Practices in Private Sector Organisations in Nigeria

Monday Osemeke, PhD

Department of Business Administration
College of Management and Social Sciences
Samuel Adegboyega University
Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria
+2348035656284 & +2347019154521
Osemeke2k2002@yahoo.com; drmosemeke@sau.edu.ng

Marvellous Oaikhena, PhD

Department of Public Administration,
College of Management and Social Sciences,
Samuel Adegboyega University,
Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria
Prince_marv_12@yahoo.ca

Abstract

The study was carried out to critically examine strategy implementation with specific focus on efficient utilization of the labour workforce and employment practices in private sector organisation in Nigeria. It also focused on organizations' selection modalities which includes: strategic recruitment from internal and external sources; techniques utilized by Nigeria's private sector organisations to achieve efficient and effective management of manpower shortages and skills. It was also aimed at finding out the possibility of employees operating without unionism in the establishment, approaches for handling worker surpluses/shortages were discussed along concepts lines. These are outsourcing and downsizing, selection practices, and implementation challenges. The study is exploratory, and synthesis revealed that most organisations that are private sector driven, appeared to be efficient and flexible as they operate without employees' union intervention. Thus, flexible recruitment and retirement process and selection of the workforce was recommended, to enable optimum utilization in production outcomes.

Keywords: Strategy Implementation, Workforce Utilization, Employment Practices

Introduction

Strategy implementation is a term used to designate the undertakings of an organisation for effective management of economic resources and the achievement of pre-determined goals contained in a strategic plan. Strategy implementation is the third phase in the theoretical framework of strategic

management process (Orlitzky, 2018)). For organisations to accomplish their envisioned future, goals are formulated aligned with returns on investment by scanning the environment for prospects and threats, resource requirements determined and then implement their strategies. Auspiciously, implementation strategy of human resource practice appears to be the most difficult part of strategic human resource management and in most cases overshadowed by the emphasis strategy formulation. Strategic human resource management is considered to be one of the most dynamic events of organisation because it embraces the organisation's complete array of strategic decision-making. Through the strategic management practice, organisations formulate sets of decisions, arrangements and methods, generally referred to as strategies that are subsequently implemented in order to accomplish the goals and objectives of the organisations.

The broad objective of this study, therefore, is to critically examine strategy implementation with specific focus on efficient utilization of the labour workforce and employment practices, in private sector organisations in Nigeria. According to Kazimi (2002), strategy implementation or strategy execution is where the real action and tasks in an organisation take place in the strategic management process, since this is where the policies in the strategic plan are transmuted into activities or actual performance. According to Stone (2014), strategy implementation involves designing an organisation's structure and control systems and evaluating the select strategies in achieving the organisation's key objectives. Other key issues include developing appropriate budgets. Information systems, HR systems (control-based or commitment-based) and policies and procedure to enhance strategy implementation (French & Rumbles, 2010). Needless to say, it is the most demanding fragment of the whole strategic management process that requires input of the organisation's resources. However, if done right, it will ensure the accomplishment of objectives of the organisation.

Strategy implementation is the process of assigning resources for the sustenance of the preferred organisational strategies. This practice comprises managerial activities necessary to set strategy in motion, institute strategic controls that observe improvement and finally realize organisational goal. It is essentially about activating the strategy so as to produce the desired result (Pearce & Robinson, 2005). Strategy implementation activities are in fact related closely to one another and decisions about each are usually made simultaneously. Effective accomplishment of strategies is sustained via five strategic factors such as staff, resources, structure, system and culture. These factors are required to be in existence for the organisation to carry out the planned strategies (Agbonifoh, 2008). Regrettably, there is escalating consciousness of the actions needed for strategic human resource implementation and that some of the required factors considerably elude most private sector organisations. This paper adopts exploratory research methodology, using secondary data and content analysis of various literatures; which cover several areas of strategic human resource implementation starting with the utilization of human resource through workforce flexibility to control cost of labour. Additionally, approaches for handling workers surpluses/shortages are discussed along concepts lines. These are outsourcing and downsizing, selection practices and implementation challenges.

Concepts of Utilization of Workforce and Employment Practices

Numerous management theories and practices such as: systems theory, scientific management, theories X and Y, human relations theory, contingency management, just to mention few, have provided academic insight into flexibility in workforce operations. This flexibility is achieved by cross-training and other innovative human resource practices. Flexibility in workforce utilization through extensive cross-training operations without union motivates workers to master a broad range of skills, which facilitate them to perform wide-ranging activities: these lead to full utilization of non-production employees, including the efficient utilization of technological innovation and computerization (Braddock, 1999). Although, most organisations achieved much of their productivity through technology, their managerial approach has also made substantial contributions. This is because the company's industry leadership in technological innovation is, in part, an outcome of its unique work environment. Major characteristics of this environment include encouragement of risk taking; challenge in the form of specific, reachable goals; the freedom to question; trust and an absence of policies (Braddock, 1999).

The efficiencies made possible by technological innovation and human resource flexibility also are evident, specific managerial and human resource changes included broadening employee skill and job responsibilities, making each employee a stockholder of company with option to buying extra stock moving all hourly employee to salaried status. educating its' employees on the innovative technology, eliminating parks such as reserved parking places and eliminating several layers in the management hierarchy which enhance productivity in these organisation (Armstrong, 2012). Other changes include wide dissemination of organisation information, adding quarterly bonuses driven by the company's productivity and increasing the level of workers involvement in decision-making. The productivity increase is made possible by these fluctuations which are responsible for reduction in the number of employees' turnover in most organisations. It is pertinent to say that the efficiencies attained through flexible work obligation and extended jobs. were accompanied by corresponding changes involving in decision-making, compensation, informality, and education (Galante. 1987).

Teamwork and it Relevance to Private Sector Organisations

Teamwork is the collaborative effort of a group to achieve a common goal or to complete a task in the most effective and efficient way (Eduardo & Michael, 2008). This concept is seen within the greater framework of a team, which is a group of interdependent individuals who work together towards a common goal (Parker. 2008). The basic requirement for effective teamwork is an adequate team size. The context is important and team sizes can vary depending upon the objective. Teamwork is present in any context where a group of people are working together to achieve a common goal.

Teamwork performance largely improves when a team passes through three processes (Conflict management. Affect Management and Motivation and Confidence building) since processes like these enhance coordination and communication between the team members and therefore, increase teamwork and collaborative work (Cattani, Ferriani & Mariani (2013). As organisations require and hire additional staff with knowledge, talents and capacity, they are gradually finding out that. to encounter the deviations and challenges of today's business world, they must substitute their old

hierarchies and formal system with teams (Philip, 1992). The capacity to get the best out of persons and to manage their job in teams has become an important skill for both executives and employees. A team consists of small number of people that have complementary skills, directed towards a common goal, holding themselves individually and collectively accountable for their own action or inaction, Within the context of this paper, small teams are a group consisting of between 5 to 20 people,

Teamwork is the cooperative and collective determination of people in a group that is directed towards accomplishing a corporate goal. According to Philip (1992), the characteristics of an effective team are: strong purpose, roles and job obligation, lack of formality, participation, listening, civilized disparity, consensus decision, open communication, shared leadership, extended relationships, style diversity, relevant skill, mutual trust, external and internal support. The requirements for effective teamwork are based on several conditions which need to be in existence before teams can be effective, One of the most significant is the exciting purpose that is served through real teamwork, The members of the team have to key into the objectives of the programme, and their managers should be able to provide frequent reinforcement in pursuit of the compelling purpose, Operational teams have members whose skills are complementary; therefore, careful selection of team member. is critical. Some companies select team members based on their personality, characteristics and their technical skills as personality evaluation tools are used for this purpose (Karzcnbach & Douglas. 2015),

According to Katzenbach & Douglas (2015), effective teams share feedback with each other. Teams require substantial training and their member' often benefit from being trained to present honest feedback in a competent manner. Another feature of active teams is that their members trust one another. As teams mature, they can become self-governing as leadership responsibilities become shared between members of the team, Such self governance reduces the aggregate hierarchy needed in the larger organisation's structure. The leadership that develops from teams similarly enhances the stock of leadership talent within the whole organization. Additionally, the essential conditions existing within the teams and compatible organisational systems are vital for team effectiveness. Compensation, other rewards and performance evaluation methods must be adapted by the team with the move from individual, to team contribution (Katzenbach & Douglas, 2015). Top management staff also require being sensitive to team requirement as considerable aggregate of their attention are sometimes referred to as "high-maintenance" entities. One observer has compared teams to a Ferrari in that they can produce high performance but they also require high maintenance. Teams are not a silver bullet solution for all organisational problems and they are often times ineffective if the conditions necessary for teamwork are not present (Armstrong. 2012).

Operating on a Non-union Basis

For a greater flexibility some private sector organisations regularly pursue strategies of operating without labour unions, which often determines structure of the organisations; affecting divisional composition, plant size and plant location (Mills, 1978). Verma (1985) examined some large multi-plant firms, having both union and non-union operations. One strategy he found among firms desiring to decrease exposure to labour relations problems. was the approach of building small new plants that operate without

labour union rather than participating in increased capacity in existing unionized plants. In addition to these organisational characteristics, there are numerous variables that affect the likelihood of unionism which include: individual characteristics of the workforce, job content compensation, industry, job satisfaction, perceptions of union instrumentality, and characteristics of union, governmental regulation and macroeconomic influences (Fiorito, Daniel & Charles, 1986).

Strategic Recruitment

A strategic approach takes into account the organisational goals and objectives. Its main aim is to align various key element of HRM like recruitment and selection so that they function in tandem with other function to achieve organisational goals. Strategic recruitment refers to a well thought-out plan that properly fulfils the needs and desires of your company. One of the elements to include in your strategic recruitment process is employer brand which is an organisation's employer brand that defines message to the world (Katzenbach & Douglas, 2015).

Strategic recruiting is an approach to winning the best talent based on three component: employer branding, recruitment-directed marketing and skilled selling. Combined the components create effective responses to dynamic market conditions in support of an organisation's strategic objectives (Votwa, 2018). So the recruitment strategy is one of the main activities of human resource management to hire the best talent and own superior competence in achieving the business target of the company (Azmy, 2019). Interestingly, having internet as a means of recruiting has added value to recruitment and it is serving a tremendous need for matching employees with employment opportunities. They provide a graphical demonstration of how the establishment is structured to include a recruitment section. There are usually explanations of career fields, job opportunities and provisions for e-mailing resumes directly to company (Votwa, 2018). The internet provides other components that must be aligned with the company's recruitment strategy and can help provide the appropriate human resource for pursuing specific strategic. There is empirical evidence of the significance of such a strategic alignment.

Cook .& Ferris (1986) posit that organisations, as a part of a major strategic change, broke with its traditional human resource practices by using a frontend strategy of combining higher selectivity with higher salaries. It had previously placed less emphasis on hiring quality and had used an attrition approach for eliminating marginal employees. One way in which recruiting can be more strongly linked with strategy is to concentrate efforts on sources providing ultimate number of desirable employees. Along this line studies have evaluated different recruiting sources to identify difference in essential work-related outcome which include: performance, turnover, attitude, and absenteeism. Unfortunately, it is difficult for research to generalize from such results. Another strategy related to recruitment i lie i the extent to which company should rely on internal or external recruiting, or a mixture of the two, According to Votwa (2018), there are a number of advantages associated with internal recruiting. These include having more reliable information on internal applicants the motivational impact of employees knowing that vacancies will be filled from within the company leads to quicker response time and a shorter adjustment period in the new job since internal applicants are already familiar with

the company. Regrettably internal engagement can lead to managerial inbreeding, which may be particularly disadvantageous in rapidly changing environments in which old strategies may be ineffective. While external recruiting has the advantages of providing fresh ideas, requiring less internal employee development, and possibly facilitating affirmative action (Breugh, 1992). Employee shortages may not even require recruiting. Aside from the obvious approach of assigning more overtime, another alternative to recruiting is through temporary help firms. Temporary workers reduce recruiting responsibilities and provide greater flexibility in matching staffing with workload requirements. Based on heavy reliance on temporary workers, some private sector organisations have even created temporary workers' programmes within their own companies and called it "management training programmes" (Votwa, 2018).

Selection of Employees

Efficient selection techniques are critical for hiring workforce that can become a source of competitive advantage. However, some skill deficiencies can be overcome by training, the additional financial outlays required in making up for poor selection can place a firm at a disadvantage to its customers (French & Rumbles, 2009). High performing companies are very selective in their staffing decisions. A number of requirements must be met before firms can make good selection decisions. First of all, selection procedures need to have psychometric properties of reliability and validity. Reliability means that the procedure, be it a test or an interview, needs to produce roughly equivalent outcome when the procedure is repeated. Thus, if an assessment is used, an applicant's score from one organisation of the test should correlate well with the score on the next administration of the test. This type of reliability is called test-retest reliability. Similarly, when a manager interviews job applicants, the assessments of the applicants should correlate well if the interviews are repeated at a later date (Asika, 2010).

In addition, better results are achieved when multiple interviewers are used. Interviews are reliable when there is a consensus between the interviewers about an applicant that is their ratings are correlated. Asika (2010) refers to this as inter rater reliability. Greater reliability is possible when interviewers can be trained to gather information from applicants on dimensions to assess with accuracy. Interviewers also gain useful information by using interviews to seal the gaps in information obtained from the resume, application and references. Selection procedures also must be valid. Asika (2010) define validity as the degree to which a measuring instrument measures what it is designed to measure. Validity refers to the procedure that predicts what it is supposed to predict. With selection procedures, this means that the test or interview predicts job performance in the position for which applicants are being selected. For selection procedures to be effective they must first be valid and reliable. Some forms of validity available to defend the use of selection tests according to Asika (2010) are: predictive, concurrent validity and content validity:

- a. **The Predictive Validity:** With predictive validation, potential *selecting procedures* of test are given to job applicant. However, during the validation procedure, selection is based on measures other than the tests. After sufficient time for those hired to have learned their job, their work performance is then correlated with test score. Tests having a significant and

substantial statistical relationship with job performance are said to have predictive validity (Gilmore & Williams, 2009).

- b. **The Concurrent Validity:** It has the practical advantage of not requiring a time lag before tests can be used. With concurrent validity, tests are administered to existing employees and their test scores are compared with their job performance. Both predictive and concurrent validations are called criterion-related forms of validity because they are validated on the job performance (Gilmore & Williams, 2009)
- c. **The Content Validity:** There is no statistical basis for assessing the content validity of a selection procedures, e.g. test. According to Asika (2010), instead, content validity is established by having panel experts on the subject to review the test items so as to determine if the test covers the domain of the subject. In content validity, the emphasis is on adequate coverage of the test instrument and the scope implied.

Testing

Using selection test provides alternative means for improving the selection process. There are varieties of tests that are relevant to selection. Some of the most common forms of tests used for selection include, but not limited to cognitive or mental ability tests, personality test, work sample or performance tests and integrity tests (Thompson & McHugh, 2009). Cognitive ability tests are commonly used to assess an applicant's competence to perform in a job. Personality tests are used for selection purposes. Gatewood, & Hubert (1998) established that the "big five" personality dimensions useful for selection are, extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability and openness to experience. Conscientiousness is a good predictor of job performance for some kinds of jobs and not surprisingly, extroversion has been adjudged to be correlated to performance in sales jobs.

Finally, integrity tests are useful in predicting theft and other undesirable behavior, even though applicants may attempt to forge their responses. Performance or work sample test requires job applicants to perform some of the actual tasks required for the job. Work samples also can be obtained from applicants for positions such as graphic designer, commercial artist or business writer by asking applicants to supply portfolios of their previous work for review.

Dealing with Employee Surpluses

In most cases organisational managers are confronted with excesses/surpluses employees in the workforce. According to Hill & Jaan (1990), there are various methods by which companies may reduce the likelihood to lay off employees. These include short-range and long-range approaches. Several of the e approaches need further explanation. Two of these are redeployment and retraining, with the latter often being required employees can be redeployed without being laid off.

In redeployment and retraining programmes, a critical determinant in the success of such programmes is managers' self-efficacy beliefs or expectations that they will be successful in mastering the new skills. Interestingly, some companies send the wrong

message (Hill & Jaan, 1990). Further, Thompson & McHugh (2009) posit that organisational management often adopt a "slash and burn" strategy when retraining effort fail to realize objectives, laying off managers who could not acquire new competencies, behaviours and attitudes. Layoffs following retraining programmes may send a message to the workforce that retraining is a futile endeavour (Hill & Jaan, 1990). However, most organisations do not make available retraining for the employees before they are laid off. According to Leana & Feldman (1990), less than 10 percent of disengaged employees receive retraining assistance from their former employers. Because governmental agencies provide various retraining programmes, the reaction of most companies is to leave such training to these agencies. According to Armstrong (2012), other approaches for dealing with employee surpluses are: flexible retirement, managing vendors of outsourced functions, early retirement downsizing and layoffs, termination strategies; let us briefly discuss them:

- i. **Flexible Retirement:** Retirement is a major change and should be prepared for. Hence, Armstrong (2012) advises that retirement policies such as when people are due to retire, circumstances, if any in which they can work beyond normal retirement date amongst others need to be specified by the employers. According to Rosen & Thomas (1989), resistance can relate to the difficulties involved in individuals determining who should be allowed to continue working. Determinations of capability to continue in the employment will presumably be based on performance and medical evaluations. It is possible to visualize the greater difficulty of telling a long-time, loyal employee to retire because of performance inadequacies instead of letting an impersonal policy serve as the standard (Rosen & Thomas. J 989).
- ii. **Managing Vendors of Outsourced Functions:** The grouping of demographic influences and a robust economy can produce severe labour shortages in many occupations. Fluctuations of workforce are normal features of the economy and individual employers may experience skill shortages of qualified managerial and professional personnel at a certain point in time. Nonetheless, technology workers have been in particularly short supply. Companies are striving to meet the demand for technical specialists through strategic recruitment (Thompson & McHugh, 2009). Gilmore & Williams (2009) posit that the essential dexterity needed for managing such relationships are different from those of direct supervision and involve the negotiation of contracts, sensitivity to the other strategic issues that are important than avoiding reliance on one vendor and the desire to retain service levels through a contractual relationship.
- iii. **Early Retirement:** In dealing with excess of employees, companies frequently reach an understanding with the workers for early retirement, severance pay and a bonus payment that enhance pension benefits. Howard (1988) conducted a longitudinal study on stern of managerial employee that addressed these concerns, and conclude that there were no substantial variances at the 20-year mark in the performance rating of manager who took early retirement versus individuals who did not. Thus, the companies suffered no loos in quality of management talent as a result of the early retirement. Gilmore & Williams (2009) study also investigated other characteristics between managers taking early retirement and those remaining. Conversely, from the perspective of those taking early retirement, these managers seem to be

motivated by an instrumentality rationale. They had less monetary concerns and stronger life interests outside of work, such as hobbies and socializing. Nonetheless, there could be dissatisfaction with the manner in which the early retirements were handled. A particularly troublesome issue was a variation in the performance evaluation approach, because it was perceived as a way of showing them out of the company (Gilmore & Williams, 2009). Finally, the early retiree's contributions to the company should be recognized with a demonstration of the company appreciation. Although, performance may have declined at some point, an employee's many years of service to the company merit recognition and the conclusion of a long career should not carry the humiliation of a forced retirement. Many companies that had maintained no-layoff policies in the past reverted to down wing and layoffs of workforce (Kochan, MacDuffie, & Osterman, 1988).

iv. Downsizing and Layoffs: Organisational downsizing in this study discusses a set of activities undertaken on the part of management of an organisation and designed to improve organisational efficiency, productivity and/or competitiveness. It epitomizes a strategy implemented by managers that affects the size of the established labour force, the costs and the work process (Osemeké. 2015). Prior to conducting layoffs, there should be cautious examination of their effects in the long run and in the short run. This is advisable in that, if a company conducts layoffs in response to short-term losses, it may find that its' long-term survivability is endangered (Gilmore & Williams. 2009). Downsizing strategies are also more effective when effective employees are retained. In some cases, the performance evaluation system may need improvement for accurate identification of such individual. Additionally, the reward system may require modification to arrive at the flexibility needed to retain them. Such flexibility is necessary because of resource scarcities that often prompt downsizing strategies, but may be obtained through future-oriented rewards such as stock ownership and profit sharing (Greenhalgh, McKersie & Roderick. 1986). Organisations should be aware that even their short-term problem possibly will not be solved by downsizing since the loss of skills and knowledgeable staffs departure based on the offered early retirement options or severance packages. There is empirical support for this caveat, as the study of declining industries, revealed that "the poor performers' organisations looked at their actions such as layoffs or early retirements as individual events without considering the long-term consequences (Cook & Ferris, 1986). It has been hypothesized that organisations having previous experience with layoffs will reduce their staff via methods that are less severe, because their managers are predicted to have more timely insight of surpluses. With this recognition, they have to take remedial action more quickly and should be in a position to rely more on attrition or redeployment (Greenhalgh, Lawrence & Robert, 1988).

Downsizing strategies, which often involve layoffs, along with other approaches such as attrition and hiring freezes, have vicious cycle problems which include: Survivors often experience overwork, stress, frustration, and declining morale as they operate in crisis mode, attending only to immediate problems; remaining employees also tend to become more risk-averse and narrow-minded and fewer resources available for research and developmental efforts amongst others; thus, precipitating another round of layoffs to cut costs (Cascio, 1993).

- v. **Termination Strategies:** Although, terminations may be indicative of deficiencies in other human resource management systems, they are often required for organisational change and have even been categorized as an organisational development process. As such, terminations may be critical for the implementation of a shift in the strategic direction of an organisation. Termination of appointment has been used where entrepreneurs, who were effective in establishing the organisations, could not make the transition to the different managerial requirements of a bureaucratic environment (Morin & Yorks. 1982). French & Rumbles (2010) opine that employees are frequently told of the termination and escorted by security personnel to their desks to pick up their personal property and then taken to the door. Although, often related to fears that the terminated employee will sabotage a computer system or other company assets, this rationale is not usually applicable. Terminations should be conducted only after prior warning, real attempts to improve the employee's performance or correct unacceptable behaviour and an exhaustive enquiry surrounding the last-straw incident (Philip, 1992). In conducting the termination session, the manager should describe the conditions of the separation, benefits, and the nature of recommendations the organisation is willing to make. In whatever circumstance, a worker has rights to post-termination of employment. The rights of the employee post-termination of employment are: Right to receive a notice of termination of employment, right to be heard, right to have an inquiry conducted, right to receive a severance pay, right to sue in case of illegal or unlawful termination and an employee can plead illegal termination.

Some Implementation Challenges of Employment Practices and Policies

Several developments in the aspect of employment practices and policies provide implementation challenges. Career paths for technical professionals pose one problem. Dual career couples provide another important challenge to strategies requiring a mobile labour force. Technical professionals, e.g. engineers or information technology specialists, often face limited opportunities for career advancement except they leave their specialties for management positions. Professionals who make such choices and serve in management positions could find out that it is difficult to come back to their previous field because their technical knowledge has become superseded. As a result, many organisations have attempted to remedy these problem by establishing a dual-career path system that allows advancement on a separate technical ladder, as the worker acquires more expertise and experience. Technical professionals need not move to the management path in order to move ahead. Dual-career path can also be used to help retain technical professionals (Bohlander & Snell, 2004). With regards to Dual-Career, couple organisations experience challenge in transferring employees due to the rising number of dual-career couple. Two-income families are now involved in a high proportion of transfers as the spouses of many employees also work. Further, the woman is more frequently moved. With women now comprising a large number of professional occupations, it is not amazing that they are increasingly the employees being transferred. An obvious problem organisation face in transferring employees involved in dual-career situations is the spouse ability to find an appropriate position. Such fears are well grounded (Collie, 1989).

Another problem encountered with dual-career couples is their frequency of turnover when the spouse works for another large employer that transfers employees. For female employees, there is a perception, whether valid or not, that they may be more susceptible to turnover in such circumstances. This perception is as follows: "Because the female manager is seen as more often following her spouse in a relocation decision, her dual-career family status is considered more of a liability. Guinn & Lori (1987) insist that, a related problem concerns travel requirements, where both individuals have jobs that necessitate extensive travel, there are difficult problems with caring for children and in finding enough time to be together. However, response to problems such as these is that more private sector organisations are adopting their policies to deal with the special issues in involved with dual-career couples.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper concluded that employers appear to become more efficient and flexible by enlargement of responsibilities of their workers. Cross-training has been used effectively in these efforts to gain flexible work assignments and employees' time had been efficiently utilized. Further to producing benefits for the organisation, cross-training has entreaties to employees when combined with skill-based pay systems. Organisational cultures emphasizes trust appear to promote flexibility through such practices as the elimination of rules and using selection tests provide alternative means for improving the selection process. In spite of several available methods for handling shortages of employees and skills through strategic recruitment from internal and external sources; the paper concludes that further suggestions need to be provided for the conduct of flexible retirement programmes for handling employee shortages. Methods for dealing with employee surpluses such as retraining and redeployment within the organisation and early retirement were adequately utilized. Finally, the challenges to strategies requiring a mobile workforce were among some of the most important challenges encountered with technical employees and conclude that more suggestions for dealing with technical professionals could be provided.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby given:

- i. Flexible strategic recruitment system should be encouraged by private sector organization to enhance productivity.
- ii. Adequate information should be disseminated in cases of lay-off of workers.
- iii. Career development/training should be taken seriously by organisations, especially in the cases of female employees.
- iv. Rules guiding retirement benefits or severance package should be strictly adhered to by management of organisations.

- v. As a recommendation for further studies, researchers could adopt broader perspectives of the topic and use quantitative primary and secondary data for analysis, whose results, if properly implemented, will enhance the efficient utilization of workforce and productivity of private sector organisations.

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